

DEFIBRATION OF SOLID WOOD WASTE AND POST-CONSUMER FIBREBOARDS: THE mTMP PROCESS

PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET

The moisture modified thermo-mechanical pulping (mTMP) process developed by IHD shows that high-quality fibres can be extracted from post-consumer fibreboards and solid wood waste, advancing the technology towards industrial adoption.

APPLICATIONS

The wood chip modification unit can be integrated into existing or new production lines of:

- Medium- and high-density fibreboard (MDF/HDF) manufacturers
- Wood fibre insulation material manufacturers
- Other lignocellulose fibre material producers

ASSETS

- Comparable fibre quality obtained from solid wood waste and fibreboard waste to that of virgin wood.
- Post-consumer fibreboard or solid wood waste can be used as raw material for MDF/HDF and wood fibre insulation materials.
- Comparable panel quality maintained with up to 25% recycled wood content.
- Only minor adjustments needed to the standard defibration process in fibreboard plants.
- Supports the development of a circular economy value chain in the fibreboard industry.

R&D CHALLENGES

- Reduction of the dust content and assurance of fibre quality during defibration of recycled wood-based products.
- Optimise fibre saturation through steam penetration into wood chips.

ECOREFIBRE AIMS TO ESTABLISH A CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACH TO RECYCLE WOOD WASTE BACK INTO FIBREBOARDS AND INTO NOVEL BUILDING PRODUCTS

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